

THE PROCESS OF ASSESSING THE QUALITY OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The article provides detailed description of the assessment process of preschool education in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Considering the very limited amount of the information given on the process of assessment of preschool education in Uzbekistan, there was a high demand for relevant information. The article sets out the criteria for monitoring the quality of preschool education carried out by the former inspection center. Furthermore the description of the new international MELQO assessment system, the history of its creation and previous research in the field of preschool education was presented. In addition, the article describes the key components of the MELQO study and the integration process of this system in Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *preschool education, quality assessment, research, monitoring, MELQO, kindergartens.*

In recent decades, research on early childhood development has begun to shift the focus from the global level to national and local policies. Long-term studies show that children's mental abilities develop most intensively in early childhood (Silburn and others, 2011; Ibuki, 1980, Steen, 2007; Decaban, 1978). Early childhood development covers the first eight years of life, the period when cognitive, linguistic, socio-emotional and physical skills are formed that influence learning and success at school (Gupta, 2016). These skills lay the foundation for the future development of children, contributing to their health and well-being. It is important to emphasize that the environment of the child during this period plays a key role in their further development, and the impact exerted at the early stages is more effective than that carried out later (Chapko and Dorota, 2015). Nobel Prize-winning economist Professor James J. Heckman, within the framework of a consortium including economists, psychologists, statisticians and neurophysiologists, conducted a number of revolutionary studies named the Carolina Abecedarian Project (ABC) and Carolina Approach to Responsive Education (CARE), public preschool Head Start programs, Investments in early Childhood development: deficit reduction, strengthening the economy, Policies to stimulate human capital, a study of Perry family preschoolers that demonstrate that early childhood development has a direct impact on health, as well as economic and social outcomes for both the individual and society (Heckmanequation.org, 2023). The dysfunctional environment of young children creates deficits in skills and abilities, which reduces productivity and increases social costs — thus exacerbating financial deficits that the entire society will bear in the future.

1. The changes that have occurred in the area of preschool education in Uzbekistan and the need to assess its quality

Since the establishment of the Ministry of Preschool Education in 2017, within 7 years, the coverage rate of preschool children in preschool institutions has increased from 27.7% to

74.6% (Gazeta.uz, 2024). Currently, about 2.9 million preschool-age children are enrolled in pre-school education programs. This indicator was achieved through the construction of new kindergartens, the development of public-private partnerships and the introduction of alternative forms of preschool education. In order to create equal opportunities for all children, compulsory pre-school education has been introduced for preschool children since 2019. Due to the rapid quantitative growth of preschool educational organizations (pre-school educational institutions), there is a need for a qualitative assessment of the system.

1.1 Criteria included in the pre-school education assessment system.

Initially, the supervision of the quality of preschool education was carried out by the former State Inspectorate for Quality Control of Education. In accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" and Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 470 dated June 7, 2019 "[On improving the procedure for certification and state accreditation of state educational institutions and non-governmental educational organizations](#)", criteria for evaluating the field of preschool education were approved (lex.uz, 2019).

The certification of educational organizations was carried out in order to determine the compliance of the level, content and quality of personnel training with state educational standards and state requirements, every 5 years.

The activities of preschool educational organizations were monitored according to the following criteria:

- organization of the educational process in accordance with the requirements of the state (up to 105 points);
- level of development of children (up to 55 points);
- potential of the head and the teacher (up to 140 points);
- state of the material and technical base and the conditions created for the development of pupils (up to 75 points);
- compliance with sanitary rules, norms and hygienic standards, aesthetic requirements and feeding quality (up to 65 points);
- results of a social survey conducted among parents on the activities of a preschool educational organization (up to 45 points);
- implementation of training programs for the next stage of training (up to 15 points).

In 2023, these criteria were revised in order to ensure the implementation of paragraph 2 of the roadmap for deepening reforms in the field of preschool and school education and the transformation of the system, approved by Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 26, 2023 No.UP-79, "[On measures for the effective organization of the Ministry of Preschool and School Education and organizations in his system](#)" the following criteria for evaluating a modern preschool educational organization were approved:

- Educational process – 170 points;
- Developing educational environment – 140 points;
- Management policy and human resources – 160 points;
- The community and cooperation – 30 points.

The final score should be accounted for 500 points (lex.uz, 2023).

2. MELQO assessment system in Uzbekistan.

However, the current monitoring process could not provide complete information about the preschool education system. The decree that initiated the introduction of the new assessment system was, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No.UP-27 dated February 28, 2023 "On the state program for the implementation of the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 in the "Year of Human Care and Quality Education"" (lex.uz , 2023). One of the goals of the program approved by this decree was to bring the quality of education in the pre-school education system to a new level. According to paragraph 155 of the decree, the task was set to implement the "national system for assessing the quality of early childhood development and preschool education", which is planned to be implemented on the basis of the international system for assessing the quality and results of preschool education MELQO (Measuring Early Learning Quality Outcomes) (lex.uz , 2023). This process will be implemented in [four stages](#):

1. Adaptation of international MELQO education quality assessment tools by taking into account national characteristics;
2. Development of a national system for assessing the quality of preschool education in accordance with MELQO standards;
3. Conducting a pilot test of the national assessment system;
4. Taking measures for the widespread implementation of the national assessment system based on the results of the pilot test.

The process of implementing the MELQO system

The development of children from an early age and the introduction of a national system for assessing the quality of preschool education are carried out in four stages

3. Changes at the global level and the history of the creation of the MELQO study

In 2015, the United Nations set the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) for the period up to 2030. According to paragraph 4.2, the task was set to ensure that "all girls and boys have access to quality development, care and early childhood education" and are prepared for primary school. This became one of the first global goals in the field of early childhood development. Although significant progress has been made in establishing monitoring systems for the SDGs, the aspect of education quality is often defined in terms that are difficult to measure.

In order to improve the assessment of the quality and outcomes of early learning, the MELQO initiative was launched in 2014, when global attention was again drawn to the field of early childhood development. The initiative, led by UNESCO, the World Bank, the Brookings Universal Education Center and UNICEF, supports the accurate measurement of early childhood development and learning, as well as the quality of the preschool environment. Given that existing measurement tools include similar elements, a consortium of leading organizations and experts was organized. It was necessary to create common sets of elements based on existing tools. These elements are combined into two indicators:

1. Development and education of young children;
2. Assessment of the quality of the preschool educational environment.

The MELQO Group of Experts also worked on adapting the measurement modules to the specific conditions of the countries, based on the experience of their implementation in 2015/2016.

3.1 Tracking progress towards goals for young children: measuring on the scale of MELQO

Several types of indicators have been proposed as part of the SDG monitoring. A limited set of global indicators have been identified for global monitoring, as well as a broader set called "thematic" to give a complete picture of the implementation of each goal. National and regional indicators have been developed to create monitoring systems adapted to local conditions. The most important indicator for the goal in paragraph 4.2 of the SDGs is "the percentage of children under the age of five developing in accordance with the standards of health, education and psychosocial well-being" (UNESCO, 2023).

Thematic indicators imply involvement and active participation in development from an early age. To track the progress made towards achieving this goal, it is necessary to measure the development of a child, taking into account the number of children in the country. The concept of "monitoring development on schedule" is not yet unified for all countries: it must be measured in several time intervals, at least once before the start of school. Thus, equality will be achieved by reaching out to all children and adapting to national goals and cultural characteristics. Measuring the quality of the educational environment across the country is also a key aspect of Goal 4.2, since without proper attention to quality, investments in preschool education may not lead to the expected improvements in learning and development.

3.2 A brief overview of the world's experience in measuring development from an early age.

The idea of measuring early childhood development has been developed by several experts and organizations, ranging from the application of epidemiological models taken from

public health guidelines to the measurement of child development. For example, the Early Development Instrument | (EDI) was one of the first and most proven tools for measuring child development. These indicators are designed to provide comparable data on children's development and learning that can be used to observe growth and development in various fields using a set of common elements. Population indicators are designed to be applied at the population level, that is, the use of these measures makes it possible to understand the differences in the results of children's development by regional and group indicators.

In addition to the EDI, the concept of a global measurement of early development on a comparable basis was introduced by UNICEF in 2007 as a first step towards developing the largest child development index in the MICS-ECDI multi-individual cluster study, which UNICEF considers to be a source of globally comparable data on early development. Over the past decade, work has been done worldwide to develop comparable indicators of early childhood development and learning environments in several areas, with the most comprehensive and authoritative data to date from MICS-ECDI. Based on data collected from family surveys, MICS-ECDI provides a broader and comparable view of child development. The World Health Organization has also created development scales for children aged from birth to 3 years, which is an important addition and, together with UNICEF, will be able to create a single scale covering the entire age range (0-59 months) (UNESCO, 2017).

While the MICS and WHO indicators focus on a small set of elements, the MELQO modules look in detail at the development and learning of a child at the beginning of formal schooling and aim to determine the effectiveness of the educational environment for children in supporting their development.

3.3 Innovations in the MELQO system

For what reason was MELQO chosen? There are four main characteristics that distinguish MELQO from previous initiatives:

- MELQO modules are publicly available, are free for all countries and can be used by anyone;
- MELQO modules take into account both the development of children and the quality of their educational environment, creating a more holistic picture of their impact on early childhood development;
- MELQO provides a fact-based measurement framework that can be adapted at the country level;
- Participation in MELQO creates additional opportunities by identifying and involving a number of local stakeholders in the adaptation and implementation process of the project.

Innovations in the MELQO system

This process is being carried out in countries around the world, and a lot of time and resources are currently being spent on similar, narrower measurement standards. The MELQO approach is based on the assumption that time and resources can be saved if research teams have a suitable tool on a global scale, but adaptable at the local level, and a simple and understandable process for integrating assessment into the country's measurement systems (UNESCO, 2017).

3.4 A component of the MELQO study

The MELQO study consists of two main modules — MODEL and MELE.

MODEL module

MODEL (Measure of Development and Early Learning) evaluates the level of learning and development of children using two tools: a direct assessment and a survey of teachers/educators.

These tools are designed to measure key areas of children's development at the initial stage of their schooling, including executive functions, socio-emotional development, and pre-academic skills (early math and literacy skills). It should be noted that the main purpose of the MODEL component is to provide a picture of what children can do; this component does not set standards for what children should be able to do. The MODEL describes the basic skills, but does not cover all aspects of child development that may be important to measure.

For each area, MELQO offers a set of "global elements", with one tool used for direct assessment with children, and the other for interviewing parents and/or educators. The "core" elements are recommended for their reasonable comparability in different countries and cultural contexts.

The tools are designed to work together: a direct assessment tool provides information about children's early learning, and tools for educators/educators provide insight into children's behavior at school and at home, as well as the family learning environment.

MELE module:

MELE (Measure of Early Learning Environments) covers seven areas of early learning environment quality and includes examples of elements useful for indexing them. This module differs from the MODEL in that it describes key areas of learning environment quality for young children and provides examples of elements of existing tools used to measure these constructs. Given the influence of cultural factors on the definition of a "good quality" environment, it was decided to focus on structures rather than on specific elements. Various tools are designed to describe the quality of classes and include questions about parenting, teaching experience, and quality support. To date, little experience has been gained in measuring the quality of the learning environment in low-income countries, so, as with the MODEL, MELE elements are expected to change depending on feedback and on-site verification.

4. Conducting MELQO research in Uzbekistan

4.1 Preparatory work for the study

The MELQO study in Uzbekistan was organized within the framework of the World Bank project "Support for Early Childhood Development". In 2023, the preparation of questionnaires and training instructions began. The materials for the surveys and observations were translated into Russian, Uzbek and Karakalpak languages. In August, pilot testing of the instruments took place in 12 preschool educational institutions in Tashkent, Tashkent region and Karakalpakstan. In September 2023, before conducting a study throughout the republic, 30 specialists were trained to collect data, and in October, a study was conducted in 100 preschool educational institutions throughout Uzbekistan. After the analysis of the pilot testing, changes were made to prepare for the main stage of the study (Agency of Preschool education, 2024).

4.2 The process of conducting initial research

In April 2024, the training of 90 national experts took place, and only 60 surveyors were selected on the basis of examination conducted at the end of the trainings. Collection of data took place in 250 pre-school educational institutions throughout the Republic. According to the official page of the former Agency of Preschool education:

"Data collection in 250 preschool educational institutions is carried out in the following categories: 4 parents from each institution (total 1,000 parents), 4 children (total 1,000 children), 250 principals and 250 educators. Data collection is carried out using tablets through a specially designed electronic application" (Agency of Preschool education, 2024).

Data processing and collection were carried out in May-June 2024. International consultants were involved in the preparation of the final report, and the results were announced in October 2024 by the World Bank and the Ministry of Preschool and School Education.

In conclusion, it should be noted that since the establishment of the Ministry of Preschool Education in 2017, this area has undergone significant and wide-scale changes. New preschool institutions were built, new government-private-partnership based kindergartens were opened, which became a factor that led to the rise in the number of kindergartens, but in the entire history of preschool education, a complete assessment of the quality of education has not been carried out. Therefore MELQO system was presented as an integrated system demonstrating the results of preschool education in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

PREPARATION AND CONDUCT OF THE STUDY

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